

Assessment of OpenMC Energy Deposition Models in Comparison with Serpent for CANDU-6 Lattice Burnup Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Accurate prediction of energy deposition is essential for modeling fuel behavior, reactivity feedback, and isotopic evolution in reactor burnup analysis. In heavy water moderated systems such as the CANDU-6, the treatment of fission-energy release and secondary particle transport strongly affects the power distribution, as constant-energy assumption cannot capture the redistribution of energy carried away by emitted neutrons and photons. This study evaluates the energy-deposition models implemented in the Monte Carlo code OpenMC through a detailed code-to-code comparison with Serpent for a standard CANDU-6 lattice cell. Three energy-deposition modes were analyzed: constant energy per fission, local photon-energy deposition, and coupled neutron-photon transport. Both codes utilize the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library for consistent treatment of cross-section data. The results demonstrate excellent agreement between OpenMC and Serpent throughout the burnup cycle. The infinite-multiplication factor differed by only 7 pcm at the beginning of the cycle, while deviations across all energy-deposition modes and burnup steps remained within 27 pcm.

Keywords: CANDU-6, Monte Carlo burnup, Energy deposition, Serpent, OpenMC

1. INTRODUCTION

In order to assess irradiation-induced corrosion effects and the degradation of the physical properties of reactor materials and components in the Primary Heat Transport System (PHTS) of nuclear reactors, it is necessary to determine the neutron, photon, and charged particle energy-deposition profiles within the fuel channels of the reactor core. Accurate modeling of energy deposition is therefore a critical aspect of reactor analysis and safety assessment in the nuclear industry.

The CANDU-6 is a pressurized heavy-water reactor (PHWR) that uses natural uranium fuel, heavy water as both moderator and coolant, and on-power refuelling to maintain steady reactivity [1]. Conventional deterministic lattice-physics codes used in CANDU analysis, such as DRAGON, typically employ simplified energy-deposition models that assume a constant energy per fission [2]. While computationally efficient and adequate for routine fuel management calculations, these approximations neglect the redistribution of energy caused by the transport of secondary photons and scattered neutrons.

Modern Monte Carlo codes [3, 4] provide a high-fidelity alternative by explicitly simulating the transport and deposition of individual particles. Continuous-energy Monte Carlo codes such as Serpent and OpenMC include multiple energy-deposition models. The present study aims to evaluate the performance of OpenMC's energy-deposition models for a standard CANDU-6 lattice cell through a detailed code-to-code comparison with Serpent. Both simulations employ the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear-data library [5] to ensure consistent cross-section treatment. Three energy-deposition modes (constant energy per fission, local photon-energy deposition, and coupled neutron-photon transport) are examined to quantify their influence on the infinite-multiplication factor and burnup evolution.

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2. CANDU-6 LATTICE CELL DESCRIPTION

This study is based on the 675 MWe CANDU-6 reactor operated at the Gentilly-2 Nuclear Generating Station in Québec, Canada, from 1983 to 2013. The reactor core consists of 380 horizontal fuel channels, each containing 12 fuel bundles arranged in a square lattice configuration and cooled by pressurized heavy water. Each bundle is fueled with natural uranium and is fully immersed in a large volume of heavy-water moderator contained within the calandria vessel. Figure 1 illustrates the modeled CANDU-6 lattice cell in both Serpent and OpenMC. For modeling consistency, the two codes employ identical geometric and material specifications. The end caps of the fuel elements and the end plates of the fuel bundles were excluded from the model since their influence on neutron economy is negligible.

Figure 1. CANDU-6 lattice cell geometry

3. METHODOLOGY

OpenMC is a community-developed, open-source Monte Carlo code designed for neutron and photon transport simulations [6]. It supports both continuous-energy and multigroup neutron transport for fixed-source and eigenvalue problems. A key feature of OpenMC is its built-in depletion capability with several numerical integration schemes [7]. In this study, OpenMC was employed to model the CANDU-6 lattice cell and to assess the accuracy of its various energy-deposition models through comparison with Serpent [8]. To ensure consistency, both codes used the Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method (CRAM) [9] for depletion. Each simulation employed 500,000 particles per cycle over 200 active and 50 inactive cycles for source convergence.

In the simplest energy-deposition model *constant energy-deposition per fission*, a fixed amount of energy is assumed to be released per fission event. All energy is deposited locally at the fission site, and the recoverable energy per fission for nuclide i is expressed as [10]:

$$E_{\text{fiss},i} = \frac{Q_i}{Q_{235}} H_{235} \quad (1)$$

In the *local photon energy-deposition* mode, photon energy is assumed to be deposited locally at the reac-

tion sites. OpenMC uses modified KERMA coefficient to account for local photon deposition [11], given as:

$$k_{\text{local}}(E) = k_{\text{local,NJOY}}(E) - k_{f,\text{local,NJOY}}(E) + \left(\underbrace{Q_{\text{fr}}}_{\text{Fission-fragment kinetic energy}} + \underbrace{Q_{\gamma,p}}_{\text{Prompt } \gamma \text{ energy}} + \underbrace{Q_{\gamma,d}}_{\text{Delayed } \gamma \text{ energy}} + \underbrace{Q_{\beta}}_{\text{Energy of delayed } \beta\text{'s}} \right) \sigma_f(E) \quad (2)$$

Here, $k_{\text{local,NJOY}}$ and $k_{f,\text{local,NJOY}}$ are the total and fission KERMA coefficients generated using NJOY/HEATR [12] with the option `local=1` in card 2, which assumes that photon energy is deposited locally rather than transported. The subtraction of the fission KERMA from the total KERMA ensures that energy deposition from non-fission reactions, such as radiative capture is properly included in the heating calculation. The fission heating is removed using ENDF MT=318 data, and re-built using the desired components of fission energy release given in the MF=1, MT=458 data.

The most accurate energy deposition mode *coupled neutron-photon transport* assumes that photons can carry energy away from the reaction site and the photon heating is calculated using an analog photon heat deposition tally. The modified KERMA coefficient in this mode is defined as:

$$k(E) = k_{\text{NJOY}}(E) - k_{f,\text{NJOY}}(E) + \left(\underbrace{Q_{\text{fr}}}_{\text{Fission-fragment kinetic energy}} + \underbrace{Q_{\beta}}_{\text{Energy of delayed } \beta\text{'s}} \right) \sigma_f(E) \quad (3)$$

where, k_{NJOY} and $k_{f,\text{NJOY}}$ are the total and fission KERMA coefficients produced by NJOY/HEATR with the `local=0` option, where photon energy is carried away and subsequently deposited through explicit photon transport.

4. RESULTS

The infinite-multiplication factor (k_{∞}) for the CANDU-6 lattice cell was calculated using the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library in both Serpent and OpenMC. To ensure a consistent comparison, unresolved resonance probability table sampling was enabled in Serpent. As shown in Table I, the results demonstrate excellent agreement between the two codes, with a difference of only 7 pcm.

For the depletion analysis, fuel pins were treated as axially and radially uniform. No intra-pin subdivision was applied, since for standard UO_2 fuel without burnable absorbers such subdivision is not required to obtain converged solutions, as demonstrated in the VERA core physics benchmark progression studies [13]. The lattice cell was depleted up to 400 days at a constant power density of 25 kW/kgU, corresponding to an average discharge burnup of approximately 7.5 GWd/tU for a CANDU-6 fuel bundle. A total of 17 burnup steps were employed, using smaller time steps of 0.01 days at the beginning of irradiation cycle to capture short-term reactivity effects due to xenon and samarium buildup, followed by larger steps (up to 25 days) at higher burnup. All depletion calculations used the Predictor-Integrator (PI) scheme to maintain consistency between Serpent and OpenMC. Both Serpent and OpenMC employed full depletion chains derived from the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library.

In both Serpent and OpenMC, energy-independent capture branching ratios were used which is derived from the JEFF-3.1 activation file [14] using PWR flux spectrum. For fission product yields (FPYs), Serpent computes effective yields by interpolating tabulated energy-dependent data at incident neutron energies, while OpenMC determines an average fission neutron energy at which fission events occur during transport and interpolates fission product yields accordingly. Although these implementations are not identical, they are expected to produce nearly equivalent behavior and may introduce small differences in predicted fission product inventories.

Table I. Comparison of k_{∞} for CANDU-6 lattice cell between Serpent and OpenMC

Code	$k_{\infty} \pm \sigma$	Diff. [pcm]
Serpent	1.11984 ± 0.00008	7
OpenMC	1.11991 ± 0.00007	

4.1. Constant Energy-Deposition per Fission

Figure 2. Difference in infinite multiplication factor for constant energy-deposition mode

As shown in Figure 2, the infinite-multiplication factors calculated using Serpent and OpenMC exhibit excellent consistency throughout the depletion cycle. The maximum deviation observed between the two codes is approximately 17 pcm.

Figure 3a presents the relative differences in the predicted concentrations of major actinides between OpenMC and Serpent at three burnup points. The largest deviations, approximately 0.3%, are observed for actinides such as ^{244}Am , ^{244}Cm , ^{245}Cm , and ^{246}Cm isotopes. For the majority of actinides, however, discrepancies remain below 0.1%. Figure 3b shows the relative differences in fission product concentrations between OpenMC and Serpent, focusing on isotopes that are either strong neutron absorbers or significant contributors to radiotoxicity. Most discrepancies are within 0.05%, with only a few fission products, such as ^{149}Sm and ^{109}Ag , exhibiting deviations of up to 0.15%.

4.2. Local Photon Energy-Deposition

In the local photon energy-deposition mode, photon energy released in nuclear reactions is assumed to deposit locally at the reaction sites. Figure 4 shows the evolution of the infinite multiplication factor for this case. The results from Serpent and OpenMC remain in excellent agreement throughout the depletion cycle, with a maximum deviation of approximately 19 pcm. Figure 5a compares the relative differences in major actinides between OpenMC and Serpent. The majority of actinide isotope discrepancies remain below 0.4%, with the largest differences observed in transuranic isotopes such as ^{245}Cm , and ^{246}Cm .

Similarly, Figure 5b illustrates the relative differences for key fission products. The overall agreement is

(a) Relative difference in key actinides.

(b) Relative difference in key fission products.

Figure 3. Comparison of isotopic inventories between Serpent and OpenMC for the constant energy-deposition mode.

Figure 4. Difference in infinite multiplication factor for local photon energy-deposition mode

excellent, with most isotopes differing by less than 0.15%. Slightly higher deviations are observed for strong neutron absorbers such as ^{149}Sm , and ^{151}Sm .

4.3. Coupled Neutron-Photon Transport

In the coupled neutron-photon transport mode where photons carry energy away from the reaction site and deposit along their path, both OpenMC and Serpent exhibit good agreement in the calculated infinite multiplication factor for the CANDU lattice cell. Throughout the cycle, the discrepancies remain within 27 pcm, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Comparison of isotopic inventories between Serpent and OpenMC for the local photon energy-deposition mode.

Figure 6. Difference in infinite multiplication factor for coupled neutron-photon transport mode

The relative differences in major actinide nuclide concentrations between OpenMC and Serpent primarily stem from Cm isotopes, as illustrated in Figure 7a. Slightly larger concentrations of actinide isotopes are consistently predicted by OpenMC compared to Serpent in all three modes. One contributing factor is the treatment of depletion-chain truncation: Serpent limits transmutation pathways for nuclides produced in negligible concentrations to avoid excessively long depletion chains, whereas OpenMC tracks depletion chains without truncation. A secondary contribution may arise from differences in calculation of transmutation cross sections for the Bateman depletion equations. Serpent employs flux-spectrum collapse while OpenMC uses direct reaction-rate estimators after the transport simulation to evaluate the reaction rate and flux integrals for the calculation of one-group transmutation cross sections. Such differences are typical of Monte Carlo depletion comparisons and remain too small to

produce any meaningful impact on reactivity, power distribution, or safety-relevant core parameters. Meanwhile, differences in fission product concentrations remain within 0.15%, as depicted in Figure 7b, demonstrating the consistency between the two codes.

Figure 7. Comparison of isotopic inventories between Serpent and OpenMC for the coupled neutron-photon transport mode.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A detailed code-to-code comparison between OpenMC and Serpent was performed to evaluate the accuracy of OpenMC’s energy-deposition models for a CANDU-6 lattice cell using the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library. Three energy-deposition treatments were examined: constant energy per fission, local photon energy deposition, and coupled neutron-photon transport.

Across all cases, the results demonstrated excellent agreement between the two Monte Carlo codes. The differences in the infinite-multiplication factor (k_{∞}) remained within 27 pcm throughout the burnup cycle, while the relative deviations in isotopic concentrations of key actinides and fission products were generally below 0.4%. The largest actinide differences, approximately 0.3%, were observed for curium isotopes, whereas fission product discrepancies such as ^{109}Ag and ^{149}Sm isotopes remained below 0.15%.

As a continuation of this work, future efforts will extend the validation to full-core CANDU simulations, focusing on neutron flux and power distribution calculations under both TIME-AVERAGE and Core-Follow conditions. The results will be compared with those from industry-standard codes such as RFSP and DONJON, enabling comprehensive assessment of OpenMC’s accuracy for heavy water moderated reactor core.

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